

Mapping Web Universe of the ZKM: Historical Reconstruction Based on the Internet Archive

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Introduction

The web is recognised as a part of born-digital heritage (UNESCO, 2009), which requires its preservation and research (Brügger, 2018; Milligan, 2024). Websites of the cultural institutions are the focus of studies to explore how museums, archives, libraries and galleries have adapted the digital technologies and web environment to fulfil their missions and adjust their practices in the digital age (Boneva, 2023; Bowen et al, 2024; Chakraborty & Nanni, 2017). The development of museums' web presence over the decades on the World Wide Web (WWW) is essential for understanding the history of virtual museums (Povroznik, 2021). As the public-facing side of the institution, virtual museums are designed to enable remote exploration, use, and reuse of heritage without requiring physical presence at the museum itself.

Web presence of the GLAM sector is often studied with a focus on the main institutional websites, which are viewed as the central elements of their digital infrastructure (Skov & Svarre, 2024). However, museums have also created numerous separate web projects, hosted outside the central website and often developed for specific exhibitions, research initiatives, or collaborative projects. To describe the complex, layered, and expanding nature of the institution's online presence over time, a metaphor of a 'web universe' was picked up. These peripheral or project-based websites have received limited attention in scholarly research, despite their importance in representing the whole web universe of a cultural institution. This study addresses this gap by proposing a methodological approach to reconstruct and analyse the complexity of a museum's web presence, including and beyond the central domain.

Zentrum für Kunst und Medien (ZKM, Karlsruhe) was selected as a case study of a project on the history of virtual museums (Digital History, 2025). During its online presence, the center developed a strategy of creating separate websites for its various projects, hosted as subdomains (e.g., globalbody.zkm.de) that functioned as satellites to the main website (ZKM.de). Starting in the 1990s, ZKM shaped its web presence, developed and adjusted web strategies

over time to suggest various interactive experiences to attendees online. These virtual interactions could serve as a continuation of the physical presence in ZKM's exhibition space or be experienced independently in remote mode only. By tracing the expansion of the ZKM web universe, emergence, evolution, and disappearance of websites, we can explore changes in approaches to the web as a technology and communication tool, and reveal how the institution experimented with new modes of presenting art, exhibitions, and knowledge, and how it interacted with audiences online.

Due to the fragile nature of the born-digital heritage (Brügger, 2018), a significant part of the websites has already disappeared from the live web (Barone et al, 2015). Exploration of the history of institutions' web presence is mainly possible based on the web archives, such as the Internet Archive or national web-archival initiatives, such as web archiving by the German National Library (DNB, 2025). In spite of capturing valuable resources for the future and tremendous efforts in archiving the web, these repositories often preserve the web fragmentarily, with irregular capture intervals and uneven coverage across domains and subdomains (Goethals et al, 2015). Therefore, to reconstruct the history of the web presence, it's necessary to explore these historical records and assess them.

The main goal of the proposal is to identify the web resources that constitute the ZKM web universe over the decades on the WWW, to trace and to map its expansion. The paper analyses the satellite web projects' lifecycles, exploring how long these websites were supported and updated, and by mapping them on the timeline, discovers periods of the web universe's growth.

Research Methodology

This study combines automated, semi-automated, and manual (visual) methods to investigate the evolution of ZKM's web domains. This reconstruction is based on an exploration of the Internet Archive. For executing the Python code, the Jupyter Notebooks were created. They will be subsequently available for reuse on GitHub. The following Python libraries were used for:

- visualisation (matplotlib)
- data analysis and processing (pandas, numpy, re, csv, datetime, collections)
- web scraping / data collection (requests, bs4, selenium, waybackpy, tldextract, urllib, webdriver_manager)
- automation and utility (time, os)
- image processing (PIL)

Subdomains were identified through filtered Internet Archive data and scraping the hyperlinks on the live web to discover mentions of the subdomains, resulting in a comprehensive list of the subdomains for further analysis. Metadata, including capture frequency, timestamps of the first and last capture, and MIME formats, were retrieved for

each subdomain at the first stage. Homepage screenshots from the first and last successfully preserved homepages were automatically captured from the Internet Archive and shaped into posters (as an example of such a poster, see Figure 1) for subsequent visual comparison to detect the main purpose of the website, to clean data (deletion of duplicates) and also to preliminarily assess changes in design and content. Initially, 146 subdomains were detected. Exploration of the list exposed that 72 of them were duplicating the content or were not captured by the Internet Archive at all. After cleaning data, the curated list was finalised for further analysis, resulting in 74 subdomain websites, created between 1996 and 2025. At the second stage of the research, to analyse lifecycles and map the subdomains, the lists of domain- and subdomain-specific URLs were retrieved from the Internet Archive. A structured URL analysis was conducted on both the main domain (zkm.de) and subdomain levels, involving cleaning, deduplication of data via digest filtering, and identifying temporal gaps in archival data. These datasets were then aligned chronologically and mapped to visualise the structure and growth of ZKM's web presence over time.

Findings

The results of the research show that between 1996 and 2025, the ZKM domain expanded into a complex web universe. Figure 2 visualises the reconstructed web universe of the ZKM. The horizontal bar chart shows the lifespan of each subdomain between 1992 and 2025, with bars colour-coded to indicate four lifespan categories: short-lived (<2 years), medium (2–5 years), long-running (5–10 years), and persistent (10+ years). A pie chart summarises the distribution of subdomains across these categories. The x-axis marks the timeline in years, while the y-axis lists individual subdomains. The lifespan of the subdomain websites was calculated based on the digest value, which means a unique hash assigned to each archived URL version by the Internet Archive. This value allowed us to distinguish between identical and modified versions of a webpage, enabling the filtering of duplicates and the identification of meaningful changes over time. By comparing the first and last appearances of unique digests, it was possible to estimate how long a website remained active and updated.

Analysis of 74 identified subdomains shows that ZKM's digital presence is anchored by a stable core: nearly 40% of subdomains have been active (and updated) for over a decade, while another 31% persisted for five to ten years, which is also significant. In contrast, about 30% of subdomains were short- to medium-lived, operating for fewer than five years, many of them created for short-term exhibitions and small-scale projects.

Discussion

ZKM's digital presence began in 90es, with a core set of domains (e.g., www.zkm.de, salon.digital.zkm.de, globalbody.zkm.de) launched or at least captured by the web archive between 1996 and 2001. These early subdomains have a long lifespan, forming the foundational infrastructure of ZKM and its media platforms. This period corresponds to the first wave of experimentation, where the institution began shaping its digital identity (Povroznik, 2024).

In 2005–2013, there was a significant increase in the number of subdomains, with many medium to long-running projects initiated. This phase shows how ZKM diversified its digital output, launching dedicated platforms for exhibitions, research projects, and interactive exhibitions. Acceleration of the web-based projects was possible due to the development of web technologies, which became more accessible, adaptable, and interactive during this period. The evolution of content management systems, multimedia capabilities, and user engagement tools allowed ZKM to explore new formats of presenting cultural content online. These advancements enabled the institution to move beyond static pages, creating dynamic web projects tailored to specific exhibitions and curatorial experiments.

In 2014–2025, a visible shift occurred with the emergence of more short-lived (<2y) and medium-term (2–5y) subdomains. These likely correspond to project-specific, event-based, or exhibition-centred initiatives. Investigating the reasons behind this trend is part of ongoing research, but this transition may be linked to technological changes that facilitated the rapid deployment of temporary web resources. Innovations, and particularly the implementation of interactive technologies based on JavaScript, are challenging for web preservation. Such segments of the websites can be only partially archived or entirely missed by crawlers like those used by the Internet Archive. This creates a bias toward preserving static content on the web archive and underrepresents innovative or experimental web interfaces. Therefore, the interpretation of the obtained results requires more elaboration and the attraction of other methods, such as media archaeology.

Overall, ZKM's history on the web illustrates a layered and expanding universe, combining a long-term foundational web structure with a dynamic periphery of exploratory web-based initiatives.

Limitations

The results of the study revealed significant gaps in web preservation, which limit the ability to formulate new research questions based solely on data from the Internet Archive. Figures 3 and 4 present the number of archived URLs for the domain *zkm.de* preserved by the Internet Archive, which expose unique URLs filtered by digest value. Figure 3 shows the whole timeline from 1996 to 2025, and Figure 4 zooms in on the initial period (1996–2014) and makes the

data more visible. We can notice significant gaps and omissions in captured data during the periods 2008-2010 and 2016-2020, when the central website was crawled irregularly. As a result, subdomains that were active during these years and could be mentioned on the website may not have been captured, potentially affecting the comprehensiveness and outcomes of this research.

Another limitation of the proposed methodology is its focus on subdomains, whereas the institution may have created collaborative projects hosted on entirely separate domains. These external domains are not connected to the core web infrastructure in the logic of this approach and, therefore, may be overlooked.

Conclusion

At the same time, the study demonstrates the limitations of relying solely on web archives, which preserve the web fragmentarily and may miss interactive, problematic for capturing or short-lived content. Significant preservation gaps and technical constraints in web crawling pose challenges to comprehensive reconstruction, which must be considered for further research steps. These challenges call for a theoretical grounding in fields such as digital hermeneutics, media archaeology, and web history to critically interpret fragmentary evidence and develop reflective methods for reading and reconstructing web-based cultural practices more comprehensively.

The ZKM's case study and analysis of the institutional web universe opens new directions for further research. It will integrate additional sources, focusing on the web-archived collections captured by the German National Library and adopt a media archaeology approach to examine materials preserved by the ZKM itself.

Figures

Figure 1. An example of the poster, created for visual analysis of the subdomain websites. Screenshots of the snapshots of letsplay.zkm.de subdomain taken on 24.02.2017 and on 11.07.2025 on the Wayback Machine, the Internet Archive, <https://web.archive.org/web/20170224103843/http://letsplay.zkm.de/> and <https://web.archive.org/web/20250711040014/http://letsplay.zkm.de/>

Figure 2. Reconstructed ZKM Web Universe

Figure 3. Number of Preserved URLs of the zkm.de on the Internet Archive (1996-2025)

Figure 4. Number of Preserved URLs of the zkm.de on the Internet Archive (1996-2014)

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